

**Beyond the Iseult magnet 11.74 T (500 MHz):
preliminary design of two whole body MRI magnets,
14.09 T (600 MHz) and 16.44 T (700 MHz)**

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1 Rationale

Magnetic field intensity is a main characteristic of MRI machines. Most of about 50,000 installed ones worldwide make use of 1.5 T or 3 T magnets. Even if dedicated machines work with a much lower field like 64 mT of the Hyperfine Swoop permanent magnet, the interest of fields higher than 3 T is widely acknowledged, in particular for brain studies. 7 T (300 MHz) machines are already in clinical use.

The core part of the Iseult MRI at Neurospin [1] is an actively shielded NbTi magnet cooled by a superfluid helium bath at 1.8 K , operated in driven mode, providing a homogeneous field of 11.7 T within a 90 cm warm bore. The first images obtained in September 2021 are a world first making a decisive step in “Ultra-High-Field MRF”.

Two European initiatives [2] have already got funding for a 14.09 T (600 MHz) whole body MRI project with various options for building the magnet. This paper presents alternative preliminary designs for such a magnet together with an even further step at 16.44 T (700 MHz).

2 Specifications and constraints

Even if UHF MRI is limited to brain studies, human morphology implies introducing the body in the bore tube together with the radiofrequency antennas and the gradient coils. Considering the necessary cryogenic insulation, the minimum inner diameter of the superconducting windings is 1 m for getting a 90 cm warm bore diameter like Iseult one. Homogeneity of the field must be at least 0.5 ppm in the brain volume. The field outside the magnet must be limited either by a huge iron shield (about 1 ton) or by shielding coils. Despite an increase in size and complexity of the magnet, this active shielding has been chosen for Iseult and it will also be retained in the proposed designs.

Choosing the superconducting materials is a critical issue. There is a current craze for high-temperature superconductors (HTS) but it seems advisable to exploit the cheapest

and easy-to-use $NbTi$ alloy in all parts of the magnet where the magnetic field allows it. In spite of a continuous improvement of HTS tapes, the screening current-induced field and the field drift problems seem far from being solved at the level of accuracy required by MRI. Fortunately, the compound Nb_3Sn is still there, admittedly more difficult to wind than $NbTi$ but with long-term experience.

Apart this constraint regarding the so-called peak-field on the conductors, there is a key constraint on the electromagnetic stresses which they must sustain. It is difficult both to model and to include in an optimization process.

We don't consider here the practical problem of strengthening the composite conductors for sustaining a given level of stress.

3 Design principles

Maybe artificial intelligence will provide the optimal (least cost) solution, but in the meantime, we rely on a heuristic approach based on our experience which gives us the following guidelines:

1. The “theoretical” magnet is axisymmetric and symmetric with respect to its medium plane. It consists of a set of coaxial coils, each of them carrying a uniform overall current density.
2. Each coil shape is a toroid of rectangular cross section. It is wound either in double pancakes like the main Iseult magnet or in layers, privileged technique for Nb_3Sn .
3. The innermost Nb_3Sn coils must create enough field so that the surrounding $NbTi$ windings are submitted to an acceptable one.
4. Two maximum dimensions are fixed, the overall length of the magnet and the outer diameter of the $NbTi$ shielding coils.
5. The unknown parameters for each coil are $(a_1, a_2, b_1, b_2, j_0)$, namely (inner radius, outer radius, end axis dimensions, current density). The necessary number of coils is *a priori* unknown.
6. The optimization process objective consists of minimizing the total cost of the superconductors, what is done by minimizing the total $NbTi$ volume after having limited the total Nb_3Sn one to that necessary as mentioned at item 3.
7. The computational tools to be implemented must allow evaluating accurately the components of the field at any point, including inside the windings, and the coefficients of its spherical harmonics expansions (SHE) in the bore region of interest and outside the magnet (moments of the stray field). They must also cope with an estimate of the extreme stresses in the windings. The so-called “*hoop-stress approximation*” is suitable for a preliminary study.
8. Additional conditions can be enforced by structural or cryogenic provisions.

4 14.09 T (600 MHz) Iseult-like magnet

On the above axial sections, dimensions are in meters. There are three innermost Nb_3Sn coils in red, five main $NbTi$ coils in red and four shielding coils with reverse currents in blue.

The *a priori* fixed parameters are the following:

$$a_{\min} = 0.5 \text{ m}, a_{\max} = 2.2 \text{ m}, b_{\max} = 1.8 \text{ m}$$

Minimum spacing between Nb_3Sn and $NbTi$:

$$\delta = 50 \text{ mm}$$

Current densities:

$$j_1 = j_2 = j_3 = 20 \text{ A} / \text{mm}^2$$

Magnetic fields:

$$B_0 = 14.1 \text{ T}$$

$$B_{01} = 3 \text{ T produced by } Nb_3Sn$$

The final coils parameters are:

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0	0.500000	0.627925	-1.800000	-0.460446	0.2d8
0	0.500000	0.627925	-0.435663	0.435663	0.2d8
0	0.500000	0.627925	0.460446	1.800000	0.2d8
0	0.677925	1.497576	-1.798515	-0.581219	0.2d8
0	0.677925	1.497576	-0.483492	-0.213906	0.2d8
0	0.677925	1.497576	-0.116819	0.116819	0.2d8
0	0.677925	1.497576	0.213906	0.483492	0.2d8
0	0.677925	1.497576	0.581219	1.798515	0.2d8
0	1.709064	2.200000	-1.800000	-0.973458	-0.2d8
0	1.709064	2.200000	-0.141997	-0.0660891	-0.2d8
0	1.709064	2.200000	0.0660891	0.141997	-0.2d8
0	1.709064	2.200000	0.973458	1.800000	-0.2d8

On each line below the number of coils one reads successively 0 (telling the code “uniform current density”), a_1, a_2, b_1, b_2 in meters, j_0 in A / m^2 .

The winding volumes are:

$$V_1 = 1.609411 \text{ m}^3 \text{ } Nb_3Sn$$

$$V_2 = 17.967660 \text{ m}^3 \text{ } NbTi$$

$$V_3 = 10.881180 \text{ m}^3 \text{ } NbTi$$

The peak-field on Nb_3Sn is 14.3675 T at ($\rho = 0.5 \text{ m}, z = \pm 0.79 \text{ m}$) with a 143.7 MPa hoop-stress.

The peak-field on $NbTi$ is 11.603 T at ($\rho = 0.678 \text{ m}, z = \pm 0.84 \text{ m}$) with a 157.3 MPa hoop-stress.

N. B.: the field produced by Nb_3Sn has been limited to its minimum possible value which leads to a peak-field on $NbTi$ implying a superfluid helium cooling as in Iseult.

For limiting the stray field, the dipole and quadrupole moments have been canceled leading to the following figure for the 5 gauss line which is at 9.321 m on the axis and at 7.905 m in the medium plane:

N. B.: two shielding coils are enough for canceling only the dipole moment, but the 5 gauss line is about 2 m further from the center.

The next figures show the field lines :

For having quasi-equidistant field lines in the quasi-uniform field central region, their equations are the following:

$$\Phi(\rho, z) = 2\pi\rho A_\varphi(\rho, z) = \pi(0.1n)^2 \operatorname{sgn}(n)B_0, \quad n = -5, -4, \dots, 8, 9$$

where Φ is the flux through a circle of radius ρ centered at z on the axis and A_φ is the azimuthal component of the vector potential. $\rho \approx 0.5 m$ for the $n=5$ line in the central region.

Far from the center, field lines are that of a hexapole with 10 straight lines in the four quadrants of the axial cut. They correspond to the zeros of $P_5^1(\cos\vartheta)$ in the first quadrant, $\vartheta = 0^\circ, 54.175^\circ, 85.333^\circ$.

The next table displays field homogeneity in a cylinder of 0.4 m diameter and length:

B0=14.100017869 T

rho	z	Br	Bz	Bt	ppm
0.000000	0.000000	0.000000	14.100018	14.100018	0.000000
0.000000	0.040000	0.000000	14.100018	14.100018	-0.003785
0.000000	0.080000	0.000000	14.100018	14.100018	-0.014921
0.000000	0.120000	0.000000	14.100017	14.100017	-0.033337
0.000000	0.160000	0.000000	14.100017	14.100017	-0.066651
0.000000	0.200000	0.000000	14.100015	14.100015	-0.176058
0.040000	0.000000	-0.000000	14.100018	14.100018	0.001909
0.040000	0.040000	0.000000	14.100018	14.100018	-0.001934
0.040000	0.080000	0.000000	14.100018	14.100018	-0.013218
0.040000	0.120000	0.000000	14.100017	14.100017	-0.030920
0.040000	0.160000	0.000000	14.100017	14.100017	-0.054221
0.040000	0.200000	0.000001	14.100016	14.100016	-0.107509
0.080000	0.000000	-0.000000	14.100018	14.100018	0.007730
0.080000	0.040000	0.000000	14.100018	14.100018	0.003704
0.080000	0.080000	0.000000	14.100018	14.100018	-0.008153
0.080000	0.120000	0.000000	14.100017	14.100017	-0.027678
0.080000	0.160000	0.000000	14.100017	14.100017	-0.043594
0.080000	0.200000	0.000000	14.100018	14.100018	-0.000824
0.120000	0.000000	0.000000	14.100018	14.100018	0.017902
0.120000	0.040000	0.000000	14.100018	14.100018	0.013104
0.120000	0.080000	0.000000	14.100018	14.100018	0.001766
0.120000	0.120000	0.000001	14.100018	14.100018	-0.022488
0.120000	0.160000	0.000000	14.100017	14.100017	-0.075238
0.120000	0.200000	-0.000001	14.100017	14.100017	-0.075774
0.160000	0.000000	0.000000	14.100018	14.100018	0.035518
0.160000	0.040000	0.000000	14.100018	14.100018	0.023936
0.160000	0.080000	0.000000	14.100018	14.100018	0.015749
0.160000	0.120000	0.000001	14.100018	14.100018	0.015975
0.160000	0.160000	0.000002	14.100017	14.100017	-0.096600
0.160000	0.200000	0.000000	14.100012	14.100012	-0.438854
0.200000	0.000000	-0.000000	14.100019	14.100019	0.082688
0.200000	0.040000	0.000001	14.100018	14.100018	0.027630
0.200000	0.080000	-0.000000	14.100018	14.100018	-0.005898
0.200000	0.120000	-0.000000	14.100020	14.100020	0.135258
0.200000	0.160000	0.000005	14.100020	14.100020	0.164900
0.200000	0.200000	0.000012	14.100008	14.100008	-0.693161

Four coefficients of the SHE have been canceled, $Z_2 = Z_4 = Z_6 = Z_8 = 0$.

These results provide a proof-of-concept for a 14.09 T (600 MHz) MRI whole body magnet with dimensions close to that of Iseult. The price to be paid is a (too) huge volume of superconductor and the use of Nb_3Sn coils in part of the magnet, even though they are simple to wind.

5 16.44 T (700 MHz) Iseult-like magnet

The computing steps are the same as for the previous magnet. One simply need to increase up to $5T$ the field produced by the Nb_3Sn coils and to increase the outer dimensions. The axial cut of the structure is shown below:

One more $NbTi$ mean coil is needed since the middle one must be split, even if the spacing is small. Its minimum and chosen value is found to be 3.756 mm

The *a priori* fixed parameters are the following:

$$a_{\min} = 0.5 \text{ m}, a_{\max} = 2.4 \text{ m}, b_{\max} = 2.4 \text{ m}$$

Minimum spacing between Nb_3Sn and $NbTi$:

$$\delta = 50 \text{ mm}$$

Current densities:

$$j_1 = j_2 = j_3 = 20 \text{ A/mm}^2$$

Magnetic fields:

$$B_0 = 16.441 \text{ T}$$

$$B_{01} = 5 \text{ T produced by } Nb_3Sn$$

The final coils parameters are:

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0	0.500000	0.707886	-2.307657	-0.483487	0.2d8
0	0.500000	0.707886	-0.470659	0.470659	0.2d8
0	0.500000	0.707886	0.483487	2.307657	0.2d8
0	0.757886	1.486667	-2.124030	-0.633621	0.2d8
0	0.757886	1.486667	-0.564083	-0.235749	0.2d8
0	0.757886	1.486667	-0.153655	-0.001878	0.2d8
0	0.757886	1.486667	0.001878	0.153655	0.2d8
0	0.757886	1.486667	0.235749	0.564083	0.2d8
0	0.757886	1.486667	0.633621	2.124030	0.2d8
0	2.096579	2.400000	-2.276583	-1.557225	-0.2d8
0	2.096579	2.400000	-1.379200	-0.765260	-0.2d8
0	2.096579	2.400000	0.765260	1.379200	-0.2d8
0	2.096579	2.400000	1.557225	2.276583	-0.2d8

The winding volumes are:

$$V_1 = 3.620607 \text{ m}^3 \text{ } Nb_3Sn$$

$$V_2 = 20.252919 \text{ m}^3 \text{ } NbTi$$

$$V_3 = 13.703579 \text{ m}^3 \text{ } NbTi$$

The peak-field on Nb_3Sn is 16.579 T at $(\rho = 0.5 \text{ m}, z = \pm 0.85 \text{ m})$ with a 165.8 MPa hoop-stress.

The peak-field on $NbTi$ is 11.761 T at $(\rho = 0.758 \text{ m}, z = \pm 0.9 \text{ m})$ with a 178.3 MPa hoop-stress.

N. B.: the field produced by Nb_3Sn has been limited to its minimum possible value which leads to a peak-field on $NbTi$ implying a superfluid helium cooling as in Iseult.

For limiting the stray field, the dipole and quadrupole moments have been canceled leading to the following figure for the 5 gauss line which is at 10.534 m on the axis and at 8.844 m in the medium plane:

N. B.: two shielding coils are enough for canceling only the dipole moment, but the 5 gauss line is about 2 m further from the center.

The next figures show the field lines :

For having quasi-equidistant field lines in the quasi-uniform field central region, their equations are the following:

$$\Phi(\rho, z) = 2\pi\rho A_\varphi(\rho, z) = \pi(0.1n)^2 \operatorname{sgn}(n)B_0, \quad n = -5, -4, \dots, 8, 9$$

where Φ is the flux through a circle of radius ρ centered at z on the axis and A_φ is the azimuthal component of the vector potential. $\rho \approx 0.5 \text{ m}$ for the $n=5$ line in the central region.

Far from the center, field lines are that of a hexapole like for the 14.09 T (600 MHz) magnet with 10 straight lines in the four quadrants of the axial cut.

The field homogeneity is as good as that of this previous magnet:

B0=16.441029560 T

rho	z	Br	Bz	Bt	ppm
0.000000	0.000000	0.000000	16.441030	16.441030	0.000000
0.000000	0.040000	0.000000	16.441030	16.441030	-0.002882
0.000000	0.080000	0.000000	16.441029	16.441029	-0.011384
0.000000	0.120000	0.000000	16.441029	16.441029	-0.025258
0.000000	0.160000	0.000000	16.441029	16.441029	-0.046507
0.000000	0.200000	0.000000	16.441028	16.441028	-0.093793
0.040000	0.000000	0.000000	16.441030	16.441030	0.001452
0.040000	0.040000	0.000000	16.441030	16.441030	-0.001468
0.040000	0.080000	0.000000	16.441029	16.441029	-0.010072
0.040000	0.120000	0.000000	16.441029	16.441029	-0.023816
0.040000	0.160000	0.000000	16.441029	16.441029	-0.042078
0.040000	0.200000	0.000001	16.441028	16.441028	-0.071818
0.080000	0.000000	-0.000000	16.441030	16.441030	0.005868
0.080000	0.040000	0.000000	16.441030	16.441030	0.002829
0.080000	0.080000	0.000000	16.441029	16.441029	-0.006127
0.080000	0.120000	0.000000	16.441029	16.441029	-0.020697
0.080000	0.160000	0.000000	16.441029	16.441029	-0.037103
0.080000	0.200000	0.000000	16.441029	16.441029	-0.037671
0.120000	0.000000	-0.000000	16.441030	16.441030	0.013477
0.120000	0.040000	0.000000	16.441030	16.441030	0.010093
0.120000	0.080000	0.000000	16.441030	16.441030	0.000963
0.120000	0.120000	0.000000	16.441029	16.441029	-0.015463
0.120000	0.160000	0.000000	16.441029	16.441029	-0.043719
0.120000	0.200000	-0.000000	16.441029	16.441029	-0.060064
0.160000	0.000000	0.000000	16.441030	16.441030	0.025370
0.160000	0.040000	0.000000	16.441030	16.441030	0.019815
0.160000	0.080000	0.000000	16.441030	16.441030	0.011025
0.160000	0.120000	0.000001	16.441030	16.441030	0.001310
0.160000	0.160000	0.000001	16.441029	16.441029	-0.044535
0.160000	0.200000	0.000001	16.441027	16.441027	-0.166336
0.200000	0.000000	-0.000000	16.441030	16.441030	0.048233
0.200000	0.040000	0.000000	16.441030	16.441030	0.029902
0.200000	0.080000	0.000000	16.441030	16.441030	0.012426
0.200000	0.120000	0.000000	16.441030	16.441030	0.042319
0.200000	0.160000	0.000002	16.441030	16.441030	0.042566
0.200000	0.200000	0.000005	16.441026	16.441026	-0.221201

Four coefficients of the SHE have been canceled, $Z_2 = Z_4 = Z_6 = Z_8 = 0$.

These results provide a proof-of-concept for a 16.44 T (700 MHz) MRI whole body magnet with dimensions close to that of Iseult.

The price to be paid is a (too) huge volume of superconductor and the use of Nb_3Sn coils in part of the magnet, even though they are simple to wind.

6 Alternative design

Attempts for increasing the field produced by Nb_3Sn so as to lower down the peak-field on $NbTi$ coils to a level allowing a normal helium cooling show that the price to be paid is an enormous volume of superconductor which was already too huge.

Alternative designs have been proposed in two patent applications on July 8, 2011. These patents were granted on February 11, 2014, (US 8,648,678 B2) and on January 12, 2016, (US 9,234,949 B2)

6.1 14.09 T (600 MHz) magnet

Three coils only are enough to meet the homogeneity and stray field specifications with the following design:

3					
0	0.500000	1.082641	-2.600000	2.600000	0.283106E+08
0	1.562810	1.942881	-2.107785	2.107785	-0.193076E+08
0	2.491934	2.600000	-1.052701	1.052701	0.266319E+08

To get this result, it was *a priori* imposed that the magnet fits into a cube the edge of which is $2 \times 2.6 = 5.2$ m long. The required homogeneity is obtained by making the SHE coefficients $Z_2 = Z_4 = 0$ while the required stray field is obtained by canceling the dipole and quadrupole moments, $M_2 = M_4 = 0$. Under these four conditions, the magnet fits quite naturally into a sphere. On the above axial cut, the dotted circles pass through the vertices of the inner coil.

N. B.: as explained in the 2014 patent, this inclusion in a sphere is rigorous only for thin solenoids.

Regarding the electromagnetic stresses, it has been imposed that the absolute value of the hoop-stress in the midplane do not exceed 200 MPa for each coil at its both radii. This is not exactly the maximum but the difference with the true maximum is quite small as shown by the following curves (hoop-stress in 100 MPa unit as a function of the distance to the midplane in meter):

From left to right, the inner coil to the outer coil hoop-stress levels, at the inner radius in red and at the outer radius in blue after changing its sign.

Although only two SHE coefficients have been canceled, $Z_2 = Z_4 = 0$, the field homogeneity is amazingly good as shown by the following axial cut of a circular cylinder 1 m in diameter, 1.5 m length along Oz and center O :

The limits of the yellow lobes are at -1 ppm from the center field B_0 and those of the red lobes are $+1\text{ ppm}$ over B_0 . The other lines correspond to 0 ppm and they don't cross exactly at the center due to rounding errors.

The number of lobes, far enough from the center, is $2 \times 6 = 12$ which means that the main non-zero SHE coefficient is Z_6 .

The tables below show that homogeneity in a brain volume is better than 0.1 ppm :

B0=14.092336727 T

rho	z	Br	Bz	Bt	ppm
0.000000	0.000000	0.000000	14.092337	14.092337	0.000000
0.000000	0.090000	0.000000	14.092337	14.092337	-0.006087
0.000000	0.180000	0.000000	14.092335	14.092335	-0.117101
0.000000	0.270000	0.000000	14.092325	14.092325	-0.799620
0.000000	0.360000	0.000000	14.092288	14.092288	-3.468971
0.000000	0.450000	0.000000	14.092175	14.092175	-11.480843
0.090000	0.000000	0.000000	14.092337	14.092337	-0.001550
0.090000	0.090000	0.000000	14.092337	14.092337	0.008744
0.090000	0.180000	0.000001	14.092337	14.092337	-0.006412
0.090000	0.270000	0.000008	14.092331	14.092331	-0.370958
0.090000	0.360000	0.000028	14.092305	14.092305	-2.254157
0.090000	0.450000	0.000081	14.092215	14.092215	-8.649574
0.180000	0.000000	0.000000	14.092336	14.092336	-0.019676
0.180000	0.090000	-0.000001	14.092337	14.092337	0.005020
0.180000	0.180000	-0.000001	14.092339	14.092339	0.171357
0.180000	0.270000	0.000005	14.092345	14.092345	0.577691
0.180000	0.360000	0.000034	14.092348	14.092348	0.783500
0.180000	0.450000	0.000117	14.092321	14.092321	-1.131836
0.270000	0.000000	-0.000000	14.092336	14.092336	-0.037415
0.270000	0.090000	-0.000001	14.092335	14.092335	-0.102966
0.270000	0.180000	-0.000005	14.092337	14.092337	0.016922
0.270000	0.270000	-0.000011	14.092352	14.092352	1.105787
0.270000	0.360000	0.000001	14.092392	14.092392	3.906279
0.270000	0.450000	0.000074	14.092453	14.092453	8.241421
0.360000	0.000000	-0.000000	14.092339	14.092339	0.162115
0.360000	0.090000	0.000004	14.092333	14.092333	-0.264309
0.360000	0.180000	-0.000006	14.092324	14.092324	-0.925938
0.360000	0.270000	-0.000036	14.092335	14.092335	-0.118894
0.360000	0.360000	-0.000070	14.092400	14.092400	4.490398
0.360000	0.450000	-0.000062	14.092549	14.092549	15.072949
0.450000	0.000000	0.000000	14.092355	14.092355	1.269213
0.450000	0.090000	0.000022	14.092337	14.092337	-0.010360
0.450000	0.180000	0.000013	14.092296	14.092296	-2.866222
0.450000	0.270000	-0.000048	14.092274	14.092274	-4.477311
0.450000	0.360000	-0.000159	14.092329	14.092329	-0.575903
0.450000	0.450000	-0.000280	14.092532	14.092532	13.869590

B0=14.092336727

rho	z	Br	Bz	Bt	ppm
0.000000	0.000000	0.000000	14.092337	14.092337	0.000000
0.000000	0.040000	0.000000	14.092337	14.092337	-0.000290
0.000000	0.080000	0.000000	14.092337	14.092337	-0.003804
0.000000	0.120000	0.000000	14.092336	14.092336	-0.019912
0.000000	0.160000	0.000000	14.092336	14.092336	-0.069034
0.000000	0.200000	0.000000	14.092334	14.092334	-0.189892
0.040000	0.000000	0.000000	14.092337	14.092337	-0.000031
0.040000	0.040000	0.000000	14.092337	14.092337	0.000288
0.040000	0.080000	0.000000	14.092337	14.092337	-0.001041
0.040000	0.120000	0.000000	14.092337	14.092337	-0.012309
0.040000	0.160000	0.000000	14.092336	14.092336	-0.052123
0.040000	0.200000	0.000001	14.092335	14.092335	-0.156645
0.080000	0.000000	0.000000	14.092337	14.092337	-0.000953
0.080000	0.040000	-0.000000	14.092337	14.092337	0.000925
0.080000	0.080000	0.000000	14.092337	14.092337	0.005343
0.080000	0.120000	0.000000	14.092337	14.092337	0.007241
0.080000	0.160000	0.000001	14.092337	14.092337	-0.006570
0.080000	0.200000	0.000002	14.092336	14.092336	-0.064585
0.120000	0.000000	0.000000	14.092337	14.092337	-0.004801
0.120000	0.040000	-0.000000	14.092337	14.092337	-0.001218
0.120000	0.080000	-0.000000	14.092337	14.092337	0.010093
0.120000	0.120000	0.000000	14.092337	14.092337	0.029425
0.120000	0.160000	0.000001	14.092337	14.092337	0.052574
0.120000	0.200000	0.000002	14.092338	14.092338	0.063758
0.160000	0.000000	0.000000	14.092337	14.092337	-0.013485
0.160000	0.040000	-0.000000	14.092337	14.092337	-0.009381
0.160000	0.080000	-0.000000	14.092337	14.092337	0.005964
0.160000	0.120000	-0.000000	14.092337	14.092337	0.040278
0.160000	0.160000	-0.000000	14.092338	14.092338	0.101835
0.160000	0.200000	0.000001	14.092339	14.092339	0.192510
0.200000	0.000000	0.000000	14.092336	14.092336	-0.026575
0.200000	0.040000	-0.000000	14.092336	14.092336	-0.024980
0.200000	0.080000	-0.000001	14.092337	14.092337	-0.014016
0.200000	0.120000	-0.000001	14.092337	14.092337	0.023498
0.200000	0.160000	-0.000001	14.092338	14.092338	0.111714
0.200000	0.200000	-0.000001	14.092341	14.092341	0.274970

Regarding the stay field, the next figure displays the 5 gauss line in the first quadrant of an axial cut:

It crosses the magnet axis at 10.301 *m* and the midplane at 8.557 *m* .

The field lines are shown below:

For having quasi-equidistant field lines in the quasi-uniform field central region, their equations are the following:

$$\Phi(\rho, z) = 2\pi\rho A_\varphi(\rho, z) = \pi(0.1n)^2 \text{sgn}(n)B_0, \quad n = -6, -5, \dots, 6, 7$$

where Φ is the flux through a circle of radius ρ centered at z on the axis and A_φ is the azimuthal component of the vector potential. $\rho \approx 0.5$ *m* for the $n=5$ line in the central region.

Far from the center, field lines are that of a hexapole with 10 straight lines in the four quadrants of the axial cut.

All that remains to be done is to determine the transition radius between Nb_3Sn and $NbTi$ layers of the inner coil while keeping the same current density.

N. B.: this is obviously an oversimplification of this preliminary design.

It just suffices to choose the maximum field allowed on $NbTi$ windings which is depending on cryogenic conditions.

The B_z (left) and $|\vec{B}|$ (right) field maps with lines equidistant by $1 T$ are shown below:

The $10 T$ line is the nearest one to the left corner.

The next curve gives the field (T) as a function of the radius (m) in the midplane:

For example, as the extremum field on the middle coil is about $-6.8 T$ one can choose the transition between Nb_3Sn and $NbTi$ layers of the inner coil to be $7 T$ which gives a $0.699367 m$ radius and the following magnet axial cut:

The Nb_3Sn coil is shown in red. The others are $NbTi$ ones with reverse currents in the blue coil.

4

0	0.500000	0.700000	-2.600000	2.600000	0.283106E+08
0	0.700000	1.082641	-2.600000	2.600000	0.283106E+08
0	1.562810	1.942881	-2.107785	2.107785	-0.193076E+08
0	2.491934	2.600000	-1.052701	1.052701	0.266319E+08

All the windings are in layers with a $36.349 m^3$ total volume distributed as follows from the inner to the outer coils:

$$V_1 = 3.920708 m^3 \text{ } Nb_3Sn$$

$$V_2 = 11.143166 m^3 \text{ } NbTi$$

$$V_3 = 17.645930 m^3 \text{ } NbTi$$

$$V_4 = 3.639626 m^3 \text{ } NbTi$$

The price to be paid for this simple design is a superconductor volume significantly bigger than that of the §4 Iseult-like one. The only way for reducing it is to accept an electromagnetic stress level higher than $200 MPa$ which was chosen for the present study. This is illustrated in the next section with a magnet of smaller volume and a higher field.

6.2 16.44 T (700 MHz) magnet

The design is similar to that of the previous one with some increase of its dimensions by *a priori* imposing that the magnet fits into a cube the edge of which is $2 \times 2.85 = 5.7 m$ long. The field constraints are the same, $Z_2 = Z_4 = 0, M_2 = M_4 = 0$.

3					
0	0.500000	1.061921	-2.850000	2.850000	0.334528E+08
0	1.562420	1.852788	-2.434818	2.434818	-0.238506E+08
0	2.770562	2.850000	-0.999852	0.999852	0.242337E+08

Regarding the electromagnetic stresses, it has been imposed that the absolute value of the hoop-stress in the midplane do not exceed 275 MPa for each coil at its both radii. This is not exactly the maximum but the difference with the true maximum is quite small as shown by the following curves (hoop-stress in 100 MPa as a function of the distance to the midplane in meter):

From left to right, the inner coil to the outer coil hoop-stress levels, at the inner radius in red and at the outer radius in blue after changing its sign.

Although only two SHE coefficients have been canceled, $Z_2 = Z_4 = 0$, the field homogeneity is amazingly good as shown by the following axial cut of a circular cylinder 1 m in diameter, 1.5 m length along Oz and center O :

The limits of the yellow lobes are at -1 ppm from the center field B_0 and those of the red lobes are $+1 \text{ ppm}$ over B_0 . The other lines correspond to 0 ppm and they don't cross exactly at the center due to rounding errors.

The number of lobes, far enough from the center, is $2 \times 6 = 12$ which means that the main non-zero SHE coefficient is Z_6 .

The tables below show that homogeneity in a brain volume is better than 0.1 ppm :

$B_0=16.440934559$

rho	z	Br	Bz	Bt	ppm
0.000000	0.000000	0.000000	16.440935	16.440935	0.000000
0.000000	0.090000	0.000000	16.440935	16.440935	0.000555
0.000000	0.180000	0.000000	16.440934	16.440934	-0.032117
0.000000	0.270000	0.000000	16.440930	16.440930	-0.281594
0.000000	0.360000	0.000000	16.440913	16.440913	-1.326891
0.000000	0.450000	0.000000	16.440859	16.440859	-4.567960
0.090000	0.000000	-0.000000	16.440935	16.440935	-0.001853
0.090000	0.090000	-0.000000	16.440935	16.440935	0.004374
0.090000	0.180000	0.000000	16.440935	16.440935	0.008700
0.090000	0.270000	0.000003	16.440933	16.440933	-0.111400
0.090000	0.360000	0.000013	16.440921	16.440921	-0.829419
0.090000	0.450000	0.000038	16.440879	16.440879	-3.389461
0.180000	0.000000	0.000000	16.440934	16.440934	-0.011177
0.180000	0.090000	-0.000000	16.440935	16.440935	-0.002786
0.180000	0.180000	-0.000001	16.440936	16.440936	0.067147
0.180000	0.270000	0.000002	16.440939	16.440939	0.256729
0.180000	0.360000	0.000015	16.440941	16.440941	0.404681

0.180000	0.450000	0.000055	16.440930	16.440930	-0.271967
0.270000	0.000000	-0.000000	16.440934	16.440934	-0.014738
0.270000	0.090000	-0.000000	16.440934	16.440934	-0.051565
0.270000	0.180000	-0.000003	16.440934	16.440934	-0.021490
0.270000	0.270000	-0.000006	16.440942	16.440942	0.426342
0.270000	0.360000	-0.000002	16.440961	16.440961	1.636670
0.270000	0.450000	0.000032	16.440993	16.440993	3.573980
0.360000	0.000000	-0.000000	16.440936	16.440936	0.090110
0.360000	0.090000	0.000002	16.440933	16.440933	-0.110196
0.360000	0.180000	-0.000003	16.440927	16.440927	-0.442035
0.360000	0.270000	-0.000018	16.440932	16.440932	-0.161782
0.360000	0.360000	-0.000036	16.440963	16.440963	1.754274
0.360000	0.450000	-0.000036	16.441038	16.441038	6.273681
0.450000	0.000000	0.000000	16.440945	16.440945	0.612207
0.450000	0.090000	0.000012	16.440935	16.440935	0.035545
0.450000	0.180000	0.000008	16.440914	16.440914	-1.269408
0.450000	0.270000	-0.000023	16.440900	16.440900	-2.082421
0.450000	0.360000	-0.000079	16.440925	16.440925	-0.555781
0.450000	0.450000	-0.000143	16.441025	16.441025	5.495590

B0=16.440934559

rho	z	Br	Bz	Bt	ppm
0.000000	0.000000	0.000000	16.440935	16.440935	0.000000
0.000000	0.040000	0.000000	16.440935	16.440935	0.000429
0.000000	0.080000	0.000000	16.440935	16.440935	0.000795
0.000000	0.120000	0.000000	16.440935	16.440935	-0.002287
0.000000	0.160000	0.000000	16.440934	16.440934	-0.016509
0.000000	0.200000	0.000000	16.440934	16.440934	-0.056976
0.040000	0.000000	0.000000	16.440935	16.440935	-0.000275
0.040000	0.040000	-0.000000	16.440935	16.440935	0.000363
0.040000	0.080000	-0.000000	16.440935	16.440935	0.001507
0.040000	0.120000	0.000000	16.440935	16.440935	0.000235
0.040000	0.160000	0.000000	16.440934	16.440934	-0.010370
0.040000	0.200000	0.000000	16.440934	16.440934	-0.044318
0.080000	0.000000	-0.000000	16.440935	16.440935	-0.001376
0.080000	0.040000	-0.000000	16.440935	16.440935	-0.000227
0.080000	0.080000	-0.000000	16.440935	16.440935	0.002906
0.080000	0.120000	0.000000	16.440935	16.440935	0.006485
0.080000	0.160000	0.000000	16.440935	16.440935	0.005908
0.080000	0.200000	0.000001	16.440934	16.440934	-0.009551

0.120000	0.000000	-0.000000	16.440934	16.440934	-0.003939
0.120000	0.040000	-0.000000	16.440935	16.440935	-0.002321
0.120000	0.080000	-0.000000	16.440935	16.440935	0.002980
0.120000	0.120000	-0.000000	16.440935	16.440935	0.012714
0.120000	0.160000	0.000000	16.440935	16.440935	0.026123
0.120000	0.200000	0.000001	16.440935	16.440935	0.037916
0.160000	0.000000	0.000000	16.440934	16.440934	-0.008392
0.160000	0.040000	-0.000000	16.440934	16.440934	-0.006915
0.160000	0.080000	-0.000000	16.440935	16.440935	-0.000979
0.160000	0.120000	-0.000000	16.440935	16.440935	0.013341
0.160000	0.160000	-0.000000	16.440935	16.440935	0.040623
0.160000	0.200000	0.000000	16.440936	16.440936	0.083129
0.200000	0.000000	-0.000000	16.440934	16.440934	-0.014005
0.200000	0.040000	-0.000000	16.440934	16.440934	-0.014067
0.200000	0.080000	-0.000000	16.440934	16.440934	-0.011407
0.200000	0.120000	-0.000001	16.440935	16.440935	0.001943
0.200000	0.160000	-0.000001	16.440935	16.440935	0.037344
0.200000	0.200000	-0.000001	16.440936	16.440936	0.106661

Regarding the stay field, the next figure displays the 5 *gauss* line in the first quadrant of an axial cut:

It crosses the magnet axis at 10.880 *m* and the midplane at 8.977 *m*.

The field lines are shown below:

For having quasi-equidistant field lines in the quasi-uniform field central region, their equations are the following:

$$\Phi(\rho, z) = 2\pi\rho A_\varphi(\rho, z) = \pi(0.1n)^2 \operatorname{sgn}(n) B_0, \quad n = -5, -4, \dots, 6, 7$$

where Φ is the flux through a circle of radius ρ centered at z on the axis and A_φ is the azimuthal component of the vector potential. $\rho \approx 0.5 \text{ m}$ for the $n=5$ line in the central region. Far from the center, field lines are that of a hexapole with 10 straight lines in the four quadrants of the axial cut.

All that remains to be done is to determine the transition radius between Nb_3Sn and $NbTi$ layers of the inner coil while keeping the same current density.

It just suffices to choose the maximum field allowed on $NbTi$ windings which is depending on cryogenic conditions.

The next curve gives the field (T) as a function of the radius (m) in the midplane:

For example, as the extremum field on the middle coil is about $-7.2 T$ one can choose the transition between Nb_3Sn and $NbTi$ layers of the inner coil to be $8 T$ which gives a $0.700798 m$ radius and the following magnet axial cut:

The Nb_3Sn coil is shown in red. The others are $NbTi$ ones in red and with reverse currents in the blue coil.

3					
0	0.500000	0.700798	-2.850000	2.850000	0.334528E+08
0	0.700798	1.061921	-2.850000	2.850000	0.334528E+08
0	1.562420	1.852788	-2.434818	2.434818	-0.238506E+08
0	2.770562	2.850000	-0.999852	0.999852	0.242337E+08

All the windings are in layers with a $33.692 m^3$ total volume distributed as follows from the inner to the outer coils:

$$V_1 = 4.317705 m^3 \text{ } Nb_3Sn$$

$$V_2 = 11.398912 m^3 \text{ } NbTi$$

$$V_3 = 15.170933 m^3 \text{ } NbTi$$

$$V_4 = 2.804940 m^3 \text{ } NbTi$$

This simple design leads to a superconductor volume smaller than that of the §5 Iseult-like one ($37.577 m^3$) which confirms the interest of accepting an electromagnetic stress level as high as possible.

Hence an attempt to modify the previous designs to reduce further the windings volumes.

7 Modified design

As shown in §6, the architectures called “circumspherical” after figures 1 and 2 of the above-mentioned patent (US 8,648,678 B2) fulfill all conditions required for MRI magnets at the expense of important superconductor volumes. The study below demonstrates that they can be reduced by enforcing adequate constraints.

The present goal is to design a 14.09 T (600 MHz) magnet within the geometric limits of the 11.7 T Iseult magnet while minimizing the electromagnetic stresses level in the windings.

There are 12 parameters to determine (nine for the three coils dimensions and three for their uniform current densities) for a given maximum stress level which is increased until the optimization code finds a solution. This is done when 275 MPa is reached, the code giving $B_0 = 14.09232 T$ with 10^{-9} relative accuracy while canceling Z_2, Z_4 and M_2 coefficients of the SHE to the same precision.

The maximum hoop-stress (HS) is reached on the inner radius of the inner coil and on that of the outer one.

The extremal HS on the middle coil is $-238.798 MPa$

The resulting design is detailed below:

$a_1(m)$	$a_2(m)$	$-b_1 = b_2(m)$	$j_0(10^8 A / m^2)$
0.500000	0.925289	1.924980	0.390259
1.313512	1.691302	1.296516	-0.232821
1.700262	2.004356	0.331943	0.264154

The outer diameter is slightly smaller than that of Iseult. The total volume of the coils is $18.929 m^3$, about twice that of Iseult, $9.509 m^3$.

The following table shows the homogeneity in a cube with an edge length of 40 cm :

rho	z	Br	Bz	Bt	ppm
0.000000	0.000000	0.000000	14.092322	14.092322	0.000000
0.000000	0.040000	0.000000	14.092322	14.092322	0.000092
0.000000	0.080000	0.000000	14.092322	14.092322	-0.002773
0.000000	0.120000	0.000000	14.092321	14.092321	-0.036822
0.000000	0.160000	0.000000	14.092319	14.092319	-0.211675
0.000000	0.200000	0.000000	14.092310	14.092310	-0.811745
0.040000	0.000000	0.000000	14.092322	14.092322	-0.000056
0.040000	0.040000	-0.000000	14.092322	14.092322	0.000134
0.040000	0.080000	0.000000	14.092322	14.092322	0.002272
0.040000	0.120000	0.000000	14.092322	14.092322	-0.007781
0.040000	0.160000	0.000002	14.092320	14.092320	-0.116271
0.040000	0.200000	0.000006	14.092314	14.092314	-0.575112
0.080000	0.000000	0.000000	14.092322	14.092322	0.000759
0.080000	0.040000	0.000000	14.092322	14.092322	-0.002291
0.080000	0.080000	-0.000000	14.092322	14.092322	0.004275
0.080000	0.120000	0.000000	14.092322	14.092322	0.048660
0.080000	0.160000	0.000002	14.092323	14.092323	0.114859
0.080000	0.200000	0.000008	14.092322	14.092322	0.048619
0.120000	0.000000	-0.000000	14.092322	14.092322	0.011286
0.120000	0.040000	0.000000	14.092322	14.092322	-0.008965
0.120000	0.080000	-0.000000	14.092321	14.092321	-0.030343
0.120000	0.120000	-0.000001	14.092322	14.092322	0.046172
0.120000	0.160000	-0.000001	14.092326	14.092326	0.322050
0.120000	0.200000	0.000004	14.092333	14.092333	0.806351
0.160000	0.000000	-0.000000	14.092323	14.092323	0.065960
0.160000	0.040000	0.000001	14.092322	14.092322	-0.003232
0.160000	0.080000	0.000000	14.092320	14.092320	-0.138131
0.160000	0.120000	-0.000003	14.092320	14.092320	-0.140047
0.160000	0.160000	-0.000008	14.092325	14.092325	0.257809
0.160000	0.200000	-0.000009	14.092340	14.092340	1.294309
0.200000	0.000000	0.000000	14.092325	14.092325	0.254475
0.200000	0.040000	0.000004	14.092323	14.092323	0.079567
0.200000	0.080000	0.000003	14.092317	14.092317	-0.329352
0.200000	0.120000	-0.000003	14.092313	14.092313	-0.644536
0.200000	0.160000	-0.000016	14.092316	14.092316	-0.385143
0.200000	0.200000	-0.000030	14.092336	14.092336	0.985197

Regarding the stray field, although the field is higher than that of Iseult and the dipole moment M_2 only has been canceled the 5 gauss line is less far away from the center:

11.302 m along the axis

8.832 m in the midplane

The following figure shows this line in the first quadrant of an axial cut:

The next figures show the field lines:

For having quasi-equidistant field lines in the quasi-uniform field central region, their equations are the following:

$$\Phi(\rho, z) = 2\pi\rho A_\varphi(\rho, z) = \pi(0.1n)^2 \operatorname{sgn}(n)B_0, \quad n = -5, -4, \dots, 5, 6$$

where Φ is the flux through a circle of radius ρ centered at z on the axis and A_φ is the azimuthal component of the vector potential. $\rho \approx 0.5 \text{ m}$ for the $n=5$ line in the central region.

Far from the center, field lines are that of a dipole with one straight lines $\Phi = 0$ in each quadrant of the axial cut together with the Oz axis. The angle with Oz of the straight line in the first quadrant corresponds to the zero of $P_3^1(\cos \vartheta)$:

$$\vartheta = \arccos \frac{1}{\sqrt{5}} = \arctan 2 = 63.435^\circ$$

The next curve gives the field (T) as a function of the radius (m) in the midplane:

It allows determining the transition radius in the inner coil between the Nb_3Sn and $NbTi$ layers. If one choose that the transition occurs at $7 T$ in the midplane, this radius is 0.644704 m which gives the following winding volumes:

$$V_1 = 2.003457 \text{ m}^3 \quad Nb_3Sn$$

$$V_2 = 5.328049 \text{ m}^3 \quad NbTi$$

$$V_3 = 9.247531 \text{ m}^3 \quad NbTi$$

$$V_4 = 2.349604 \text{ m}^3 \quad NbTi$$

$$V_1 + V_2 + V_3 + V_4 = 18.928641 \text{ m}^3$$

The radii of the dotted circles of the next figure are:

$$r_1 = 1.988856 \text{ m}, \quad r_2 = 2.135815 \text{ m}$$

The following field maps are needed for a detailed analysis of stresses in the windings:

The B_z map is on the left and the $|\vec{B}|$ one is on the right with lines equidistant by $1 T$ between $14 T$ (the most intense red line on both figures) and $1 T$ (the outer blue line on the right figure). On the left figure, the two lines crossing the upper edge and that crossing the right edge are $0 T$ lines. One can thus deduce the field corresponding to each line in both figures.

From the B_z map, one can calculate the hoop-stresses (HS) in each coil and draw the iso-HS contours which are necessary to understand a rather complicated picture.

The following figures show the iso-HS contours in a half axial section of the inner coil. Lines equally spaced by $40 MPa$ go from $-240 MPa$ in blue near the outer radius to $+240 MPa$ in red near to the inner radius. The dimensions are the real ones on the left figure while the radius axis scale has been expanded on the right for greater clarity.

The coil is compressed radially. The curves below show the $HS(z)$ function at the inner radius in red and the $-HS(z)$ function at the outer radius in blue:

Similar figures are shown below, on the left for the middle coil and on the right for the outer one.

The outer coil is compressed radially like the inner one but it is the opposite for the middle coil. As a consequence, the middle coil must be fretted (shrink-fitted) which makes it necessary an external spacing on both sides which is no problem on the inner side but makes it necessary to keep a minimum spacing on the outer one, 8.96 mm for the present design.

8 Shimming

The Iseult magnet is equipped with superconducting shims but experience has shown that it was not advisable to use them because of their coupling to the gradients. Therefore, its shimming is done by iron platelets close to the outer radius of the bore where they are super-magnetized. This works perfectly well but for higher field magnets such arrangements may be too weak. It is thus important to seek an alternative or just complementary solution.

For all “circumspherical” magnets, there is a large region between the inner coil and the next surrounding one where exists a magnetic field high enough to super-saturate ferromagnetic pieces. They can be made of iron or of other materials with a higher magnetization.

As an example, the following field maps show the B_z component of the field in this intermediate region of the present magnet:

Lines equally spaced by $0.5 T$ go from $-7 T$ in blue near the outer radius to $-1.5 T$ in red near the right upper corner of the half axial cut. The dimensions in meter are the real ones on the left figure while the radius axis scale has been expanded on the right for greater clarity. There is obviously enough space for installing ferromagnetic pieces which will be super-saturated as shown by the following curve $-B_z(z, \rho = 1 m)$:

What is difficult here is finding how to install the shimming pieces.

Installing them inside the cryostat implies the following process: after charging the magnet to its nominal field and mapping it, the necessary shimming is calculated. Then, the magnet is discharged, warmed up and this shimming is installed in the cryostat. After cooling and recharging the magnet, it is unlikely that the shimming would be perfect but it should be easily complemented by an additional one in the bore tube.

However, a system can be conceived along the lines of the U.S. Patent 5,047,720 where ferromagnetic pellets separated by non-magnetic spacers are inserted into tubes parallel to Oz arranged in a ring between the two innermost coils. The problem of insulating these tubes to allow charging them without warming up the magnet is a problem left to cryogenics.

A more radical solution would be to implement two separate cryostats, one for the inner $Nb_3Sn|NbTi$ coil and the other for the two $NbTi$ coils (middle and outer), while leaving enough radial space for the shimming set. The mechanical structure should implement a full capability of adjusting their relative position (six parameters) which is of interest for perfect tuning.

9 Conclusion

The objective of this work was to provide an overview on possible designs of Ultra-High-Field MRI magnets relying on proven technical solutions. They can stand as a reference for alternative HTS concepts.

10 References

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